

Absolute EAG amplitude (-MV)

1. Electroantennogram responses of *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis* to pheromone standards. * Indicates a significant higher response.

Integrated pest management – other pests

Correlation between *Hirschmanniella oryzae* population and rice grain weight

L. Arayarungsarit and S. Junbuathong, Pathumthani Rice Research Center, Thanyahuri Pathumthani 12110, Thailand

We collected 20 plant samples of rice variety RD10 at ripening randomly from the experimental field in 1989 wet season. The number of rice root nematodes *Hirschmanniella oryzae* extracted from roots was compared with grain weight of each sample.

The correlation coefficient between number of nematodes in 1 g root with 100-grain weight was -0.677. The regression analysis of a linear model for the number of nematodes in roots (X) and 100-grain weight (Y) was $Y = 2.942 - 0.002X$ (see figure).

We also compared the nematode population in 1 g root with plant height. The correlation coefficient was not significant. ■

% EAG relative to standard (1-hexanol)

2. Dose response curves of *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis* for Z13-18:Ac and Z11-16:Ac.

tively fixed at 96:4 for *M. patnalis* and 2:98 for *C. medinalis*.

Further analysis of a larger number of pheromone gland extracts and behavioral

studies with different ratios of the two compounds are needed to determine the blend that is most effective for monitoring the two LF species. ■

Estimated regression of grain weight of RD10 because of *Hirschmanniella oryzae* population under field conditions at Pathumthani Rice Research Center, 1989. ** = significant at the 1% level.